

Project acronym: **SPOT**
Project full title: **Social and innovative platform on cultural tourism and its potential towards deepening Europeanisation**

SPOT – DELIVERABLE

SPOT project website

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Disclaimer:

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¹ Nature: R = Report, P = Prototype, D = Demonstrator, O = Other

² Dissemination level:

PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Purpose and scope of the deliverable:

The objective of D4.1 is to set up and launch SPOT project website at www.spotprojecth2020.eu. The web-site must secure sufficient public visibility of the project, enable effective communication with stakeholders and wider audiences as well serve as an internal collaboration tool for the consortium members.

Document history

<i>Version</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Description</i>
0.1	27.02.2020	Draft report compiled by KRTK, restricted circulation
0.2	27.02.2020	Improved draft produced by Alexander Chvorostov, restricted circulation
0.3	28.02.2020	Draft revised by KRTK and MENDELU, circulated among PMB members
1.0 (final)	29.02.2020	Approved by PMB and the Coordinator and submitted to EC

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1 Overall description

1.1 Objectives and scope of the deliverable

The objective of D4.1 is to set up and launch SPOT project website at www.spotprojecth2020.eu. The web-site must secure sufficient public visibility of the project, enable effective communication with stakeholders and wider audiences as well serve as an internal collaboration tool for the consortium members.

1.2 Production and technical details

The initial design of SPOT-web is done by KRTK using the service of the freely available WIX platform (www.wix.com); the domain name has been purchased and is administered by MENDELU.

The public part of the site is placed at <http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/>, while the restricted area for SPOT project members is situated on the FTP server of KRTK.

SPOT-web is optimized both for desktop computers and mobile Android and Apple devices.

After an inception phase and testing, the site went online at its regular URL on 27 February 2020, though with limited functionality so far.

It is envisioned the further improvements of SPOT web-site in terms of its design, interface and further extended functionalities will be implemented during the next four months (by 30 June 2020).

2 Structure of SPOT project website

SPOT website serves as a main public project presentation and information tool and has an additional functionality of a consortial collaborative platform.

Figure 1. The overall view of the starting page of SPOT-web area (desktop computer view)

2.1 SPOT web-space, its main components and menu items

The SPOT web-space is subdivided into two main areas – the publicly available pages and pages with restricted access only for project members.

One can navigate to individual pages and sub-pages using the means of the main menu that is structured as follows:

- **HOME** (public) is a welcome page and a main entrance to SPOT web-space. It contains a dashboard that displays the most actual information about the project;
- **THE PROJECT** (public) contains the overall description of the project, its main components and mission;
- **CASE STUDIES** (public) presents overviews of all 15 individual case studies that will be implemented by project teams;
- **PARTNERS** (public) introduces all members of SPOT project consortium;
- **PUBLICATIONS** (public) is reserved for the collection all project-related publications of all teams;
- **SPOT-IT TOOL** (public) is a presentation of the forthcoming innovative tool that is being developed by one of the project partners (BUI) and that will be available for wider audiences in several stages of production;
- **EVENTS & NEWS** (public) displays ongoing project news and events as well as contains an archive of the related items;
- **CONTACT** (public) has two major components: (a) a geographical map that locates each project partner using the Google Map tool as well as (b) a contact form than enables sending messages and enquiries to WP4 Team;
- **INTRANET** (restricted access) is an area for internal project data storage and collaborative platform for the collective work on project's products (reports, deliverables, etc.)

Figure 2. Interactive map of Case studies and partners

2.2 Further functionalities

- **Internal search engine** that helps visitors finding particular contents on the SPOT web based on user's enquiries;
- **Subscription service** for the potential recipients of project newsletters, updates and other important information about the project.
- **Link to CORDIS database**, namely to the entry that contains official information about the EU-funded SPOT project.

Figure 3. SPOT web-header (main menu and the internal search engine window)

Figure 4. SPOT subscription service

Figure 5. Link to CORDIS and the acknowledgement of funding

2.3 Restricted area (intranet)

INTRANET is an internal FTP server that facilitates file sharing between project members and creates a live connection between institutes.

Members of all SPOT partner's teams will be able to use the restricted domain of the website to share information and work on jointly authored documents. The various databases of collected information might be stored in the restricted area as well.

Figure 6. SPOT – INTRANET page

3 Further development and updates

The further development and update of SPOT website is already scheduled. The detailed requirements for website improvement are being developed now and will be subject to review and subsequent approval by the Project Management Board. Our target is to have launched an upgraded version of the site by 30 June 2020. Once re-designed, the SPOT website will be still available at its regular URL (www.spotprojecth2020.eu) and will be continuously maintained and administered by the SPOT consortium.